

Fairness-regularized geographically weighted regression for urban accessibility analysis

Pepa Ramírez-Cobo^{a,*}, Ismael Montero^a

^a*Department of Statistics and Operations Research, University of Cádiz, Spain*

Abstract

The increasing use of predictive models in socially sensitive domains has intensified concerns regarding the reproduction of historical biases affecting vulnerable population groups. Although fairness-aware machine learning has developed numerous methodologies to mitigate unfair predictive behaviour, these approaches have been largely concentrated on non-spatial applications such as finance, healthcare, or recommendation systems. In contrast, urban-planning studies have extensively documented socio-spatial disparities related to accessibility to public services and urban opportunities. Consequently, predictive models trained on urban data reflecting such inequalities may perpetuate or intensify existing accessibility gaps.

Motivated by real urban-accessibility datasets exhibiting significant socioeconomic disparities, this paper introduces a fairness-regularized extension of geographically weighted regression (GWR). Specifically, the proposed methodology incorporates explicit fairness constraints into the classical locally weighted least-squares formulation in order to regulate predictive disparities between sensitive and non-sensitive population groups. The resulting constrained regression problem can be efficiently solved using standard quadratic-optimization routines.

The proposed methodology is illustrated through two urban-accessibility case studies in the city of Seville (Spain) involving Urban Green Spaces and Healthcare Facilities datasets. Numerical experiments reveal a clear trade-off between predictive accuracy and fairness, while

*Corresponding author

Email addresses: pepa.ramirez@uca.es (Pepa Ramírez-Cobo), ismael.montero@uca.es (Ismael Montero)

also highlighting the spatial redistributive effects induced by fairness constraints.

Keywords: Algorithmic fairness, Geographically weighted regression, Spatial accessibility, Urban analytics, Fairness-aware prediction, Urban planning, Spatial data science

1. Introduction

Modern machine-learning models are routinely employed in domains with strong implications for human well-being, including healthcare, finance, education, criminal justice, and public administration. When these algorithms are trained using historical datasets containing socially sensitive attributes or reflecting pre-existing societal imbalances, their predictions may reproduce or even amplify disparities affecting vulnerable population groups. Motivated by these concerns, fairness-aware machine learning has emerged as a prominent research field devoted to detecting, quantifying, and mitigating unfair predictive behaviour; see, for example, Oneto and Chiappa (2020); Caton and Haas (2024); Mehrabi et al. (2021); Carrizosa et al. (2024). Most existing fairness-oriented approaches have focused on regression or classification problems arising in domains such as finance, healthcare, criminal justice, or recommendation systems, see Hort et al. (2024); Le Quy et al. (2022). Many of these methodologies rely on in-processing fairness strategies in which the predictive model itself is modified during the training stage in order to explicitly regulate or mitigate unfair predictive behaviour. Typically, this is achieved by incorporating fairness-aware regularization terms, constraints, or alternative optimization criteria directly into the model-calibration procedure, see Zafar et al. (2019); Yu et al. (2025).

Fairness in spatial prediction and urban-planning applications has received comparatively limited attention, despite the extensive urban literature documenting substantial disparities affecting vulnerable population groups defined according to race, gender, age, family structure, immigration status, or income level. These disparities are frequently reflected in unequal accessibility conditions to urban services, green spaces, healthcare facilities, transportation systems, and housing opportunities; see, for example, Fainstein (2010); Gilderbloom and Rosentraub (1990); Koprowska et al. (2020); Kim et al. (2022); Shahraki (2021); Wang

et al. (2022). In consequence, if urban-planning analyses and decision-making processes rely on predictive models trained using such biased urban data, the disparities may persist or become intensified in the resulting predictions Mehrabi et al. (2021). Kontokosta and Hong (2021) provides a representative example of how socio-spatial biases present in urban datasets may ultimately affect data-driven smart-city decision-making processes. These concerns reinforce the need to incorporate fairness considerations into the predictive spatial models increasingly used in urban analysis and planning applications, a challenge that has been recently highlighted by some authors; see, for example, Janowicz (2023), Saxena et al. (2024) or Singleton and Spielman (2026). It is important to remark that some recent literature has addressed the concept of spatial fairness, see Saxena et al. (2024), a fairness notion that differs from the one considered in this work. There, the sensitive attribute is directly associated with the geographical location itself or with spatially defined regions. In contrast, the present paper considers sensitive groups defined through socioeconomic attributes — such as income level or demographic characteristics — while explicitly incorporating spatial heterogeneity through a spatial regression model.

Specifically, the methodology adopted in this work is Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR), Brunson et al. (1996, 1998); Fotheringham et al. (2003), a widely used methodology for modeling spatially heterogeneous relationships. Unlike global regression approaches, GWR allows regression coefficients to vary spatially across the study region, enabling the analysis of spatially heterogeneous relationships between the variables under study. Since its introduction, GWR has motivated a large body of methodological research and numerous extensions aimed at addressing increasingly complex spatial-analysis scenarios, see Dong et al. (2018), Gao et al. (2022), Hu et al. (2023), Fotheringham et al. (2023), Yu (2025), as a few examples.

This paper introduces a fairness-aware extension of the GWR model. Specifically, we propose an in-processing fair GWR approach in which fairness constraints are directly incorporated into the local regression calibration procedure. The proposed approach is built upon a group-fairness criterion that quantifies predictive disparities between sensitive and

non-sensitive population groups through differences in average predicted accessibility levels. The resulting methodology formulates the fair GWR estimation process as a constrained optimization problem in which the locally weighted least-squares objective is combined with explicit unfairness-control constraints. In this way, the proposed method allows the level of predictive unfairness to be directly regulated while preserving the spatial heterogeneity captured by the GWR model. The novel approach is illustrated through two real urban-accessibility case studies in the city of Seville (Spain). The first experiment considers globally imposed fairness constraints across the entire municipality, whereas the second explores a territorially targeted fairness intervention focused on particularly vulnerable census tracts. The numerical experiments reveal the trade-off between predictive accuracy and unfairness reduction, while also illustrating the spatial redistributive effects induced by fairness-aware prediction model.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the urban-accessibility datasets considered in the study, defines the sensitive population groups and accessibility-disparity measures, and presents several motivating real examples illustrating the existence of urban inequalities. Section 3 reviews the fundamentals of GWR and introduces the proposed fairness-regularized GWR model together with the corresponding optimization formulation and estimation procedure. Section 4 illustrates the proposed fair GWR methodology using the urban-accessibility case studies previously introduced in Section 2, considering both globally imposed and territorially targeted fairness constraints. Finally, Section 5 concludes the paper and discusses possible future research directions.

2. Urban accessibility data and motivating examples

This section introduces the motivating urban-accessibility scenarios underlying the methodological contribution proposed in this work, namely, a fairness-regularized extension of the GWR model. First, we briefly describe the UrbanIneq platform, a recent open urban-data infrastructure from which the urban-accessibility datasets used throughout this work have

been obtained. Next, we introduce the sensitive population groups and accessibility-disparity measures that will subsequently be incorporated into the proposed fair GWR methodology. Finally, two motivating urban-accessibility examples obtained from UrbanIneq datasets are presented. These examples will later serve in Section 4 to illustrate the behavior of the proposed fairness-aware spatial regression model.

2.1. UrbanIneq accessibility datasets

As discussed in Section 1, numerous studies in urban planning have reported disparities in accessibility to essential urban services across different population groups. Such inequalities are frequently associated with socioeconomic characteristics including income level, unemployment, age structure, or demographic vulnerability.

This work is motivated by two real examples obtained from the UrbanIneq platform (Jiménez-Revuelta et al., 2026), an open urban-data infrastructure that integrates publicly available information from OpenStreetMap, the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE), and the Andalusian Institute of Statistics and Cartography (IECA). The platform currently provides harmonized accessibility and socioeconomic information for the 785 municipalities of the Andalusian region. For each municipality, the generated datasets contain an accessibility indicator Y together with seven socioeconomic attributes measured at census-tract level, denoted by X_1, \dots, X_7 , and summarized in Table 1.

Variable	Definition
Y	(min/avg/max) walking distance to UGS/HCF
X_1	Total population
X_2	Average net income per capita (euros)
X_3	Proportion of population aged below 18 (%)
X_4	Proportion of population aged above 64 (%)
X_5	Unemployment rate (%)
X_6	Proportion of foreign population (%)
X_7	Loneliness index (%)

Table 1: Socioeconomic variables and accessibility indicators composing the UrbanIneq dataset structure.

The indicator Y represents a network-based accessibility measure computed through

walking distances over the OpenStreetMap street network. Specifically, Y corresponds to a user-selected minimum, average, or maximum walking distance between census-tract centroids and selected urban facilities, namely Urban Green Spaces (UGS) or Healthcare Facilities (HCF). Regarding the socio-economic attributes X_1, \dots, X_7 , as discussed in the following sections, they will allow the identification of population groups potentially exposed to less favourable accessibility conditions.

2.2. Sensitive groups and accessibility disparity

Consider a municipality partitioned into N census tracts indexed by $\{1, \dots, N\}$ and let $Y = (y_1, \dots, y_N)$ represent the corresponding accessibility measurements (minimum, average or maximum distances) for the considered urban facility, either UGS or HCF. For a given socioeconomic variable in Table 1, X_j , the census tracts are divided into two groups according to the sample median of X_j . Specifically,

$$S = \{i : X_j(i) \geq \text{med}(X_j)\},$$

and

$$\bar{S} = \{1, \dots, N\} \setminus S.$$

To quantify potential accessibility disparities associated with attribute X_j , we define the following measure:

$$u_y = |\bar{y}_S - \bar{y}_{\bar{S}}|, \tag{1}$$

where

$$\bar{y}_S = \frac{1}{\text{card}(S)} \sum_{i \in S} y_i, \quad \bar{y}_{\bar{S}} = \frac{1}{\text{card}(\bar{S})} \sum_{i \in \bar{S}} y_i.$$

The quantity u_y measures the absolute difference between the average distances observed for the sensitive group S and its complementary non-sensitive group \bar{S} . Conceptually, this measure is related to group-fairness notions commonly considered in fairness-aware machine learning, where disparities are quantified through differences in conditional expectations across

sensitive population groups, see Caton and Haas (2024).

Large values of u_y indicate substantial accessibility disparities between the sensitive and non-sensitive groups associated with attribute X_j . In such cases, the corresponding socioeconomic attribute may be regarded as a sensitive attribute from the perspective of accessibility disparities. Smaller values of u_y therefore correspond to more balanced average accessibility conditions between both population groups. In the present work, the quantity u_y associated with the observed accessibility measurements is interpreted as an indicator of accessibility unfairness between the considered groups. As discussed in Section 3, the proposed fairness-regularized GWR methodology will incorporate an analogous quantity computed from the predicted accessibility values in order to explicitly control the level of predictive unfairness produced by the regression model.

2.3. Motivating examples

Seville is the capital city of the Andalusian region, located in southern Spain, and constitutes one of the largest urban areas in the country. The municipality has approximately 685,000 inhabitants distributed across $N = 523$ census tracts exhibiting socioeconomic and spatial heterogeneity. Owing to its size and urban relevance within the Andalusian context, Seville constitutes a representative case study for illustrating the accessibility-disparity analyses considered in this work. The datasets used throughout the paper correspond to the centroid-adjusted version described in Jiménez-Revuelta et al. (2026), where alternative representative locations were manually defined for a small number of large census tracts combining densely populated urban nuclei with extensive sparsely populated areas.

Throughout the paper, the accessibility indicator Y introduced in Section 2.1 is defined using average walking distances¹. Specifically, y_i denotes the average walking distance from census tract i to the set of urban facilities considered in the corresponding accessibility analysis

¹As previously commented, alternative accessibility metrics are also available through the UrbanIneq platform. Although such definitions may lead to different spatial accessibility patterns, the comparison of accessibility metrics is beyond the scope of the present work, whose primary objective is to propose a novel fairness-aware spatial regression methodology.

for the city of Seville, namely Urban Green Spaces (UGS) or Healthcare Facilities (HCF).

Example 1.

In the first motivating example, we specifically focus on accessibility to UGS, a dimension of urban well-being that has been extensively studied in the urban-planning literature due to its strong social, environmental, and public-health implications, see White et al. (2013); Ma et al. (2019); Kim et al. (2022); European Environment Agency (2021). Figure 1 illustrates the geographical distribution of Urban Green Spaces (UGS) across the municipality of Seville.

Figure 1: Spatial distribution of Urban Green Spaces (UGS) in Seville.

Consider the socioeconomic attribute X_3 , corresponding to the proportion of population aged below 18. Census tracts with child-population proportions above the sample median exhibit an average accessibility value of $y_S = 5577.401$ meters, compared with $y_{\bar{S}} = 5129.737$ meters for the remaining census tracts, yielding an absolute disparity of approximately $u_y = 448$ meters (8.73%). Although moderate in magnitude, this disparity may still reflect non-negligible differences in accessibility conditions affecting areas with higher concentrations of child population. It is important to remark that accessibility to urban green spaces for children has become a relevant topic in the urban-planning literature; see, for example, Reyes et al. (2014); Vidal and Castro Seixas (2022); Teeuwen et al. (2025).

Figure 2 presents the distribution of the accessibility indicator Y together with the distribution of the selected socioeconomic attribute X_3 . The spatial patterns displayed in Figure 2 reveal that several census tracts with relatively high child-population proportions are located in areas exhibiting larger accessibility values, particularly outside the central urban core.

Figure 2: Spatial patterns of the accessibility indicator Y associated with UGS (left) and the proportion of child population (X_3 , right) across census tracts in Seville.

Example 2.

In the second motivating example, we consider accessibility to Healthcare Facilities (HCF), including both public and private medical centers distributed across the municipality of Seville. Figure 3 displays the geographical distribution of the healthcare facilities considered in this second illustrative example. In this case study, we focus on the socioeconomic attribute X_2 , corresponding to average net income per capita. Since lower income values are associated with greater socioeconomic vulnerability, the sensitive group S is defined here using census tracts with income levels below the sample median. Census tracts with income levels above the sample median exhibit an average accessibility value of $y_{\bar{S}} = 4701.41$ meters, whereas census tracts below the median income level present an average value of $y_S = 5499.71$ meters. The resulting accessibility disparity corresponds to an absolute difference of approximately

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of Healthcare Facilities (HCF) in Seville.

$u_y = 798.30$ meters and a relative difference close to 17%. These values suggest the existence of noticeably less favourable accessibility conditions to healthcare services in lower-income areas.

Figure 4 illustrates the configuration of accessibility to HCF alongside the distribution of the income attribute X_2 . The spatial comparison between the accessibility indicator Y and the income variable X_2 reveals a clear pattern in Seville. Central areas tend to show both higher incomes and better accessibility conditions, suggesting the existence of socio-spatial inequalities in access to healthcare facilities. In contrast, lower-accessibility census tracts (darker shades in Y) are mainly located in peripheral areas and generally coincide with lower-income levels. In particular, the northeastern area of the study region, which mainly corresponds to the Este-Alcosa-Torreblanca district, exhibits both lower income levels and poorer healthcare accessibility conditions. This district is known for its socioeconomic vulnerability within Seville and motivates the fairness-oriented analysis developed in Section 4.2.

3. Fairness-Constrained Geographically Weighted Regression

The two motivating examples presented in the previous section illustrate the existence of accessibility disparities across population groups characterized by different socioeconomic conditions in Seville, thereby motivating the fairness-aware spatial regression framework

Figure 4: Spatial patterns of the accessibility indicator Y associated with HCF (left) and average net income per capita (X_2 , right) across census tracts in Seville.

developed in this section. First, a brief overview of Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) methodology is provided. Next, a fairness-constrained extension of the GWR model is introduced in order to explicitly regulate predictive accessibility disparities between sensitive and non-sensitive groups. Finally, additional computational and optimization details associated with the numerical resolution of the proposed fair GWR formulation are discussed.

3.1. Preliminaries on GWR

Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) (Brunsdon et al., 1996) is a local weighted regression model in which a different weight matrix is associated with each geographic location, leading to regression coefficients that vary spatially across the study region. These weights are typically defined according to the proximity between locations, so that nearby observations exert a stronger influence on the local parameter estimates than distant ones. In this section, we briefly introduce the GWR formulation and notation that will be used to define the proposed fairness-aware extension.

Assume that the observed response variable at location $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is denoted by y_i , and let $\mathbf{y} = (y_1, \dots, y_N)^T$. Let \mathbf{X} denote the $N \times (p + 1)$ design matrix, whose i -th row is given by

$$\mathbf{x}_i^T = (1, x_{i1}, \dots, x_{ip}),$$

where x_{ij} denotes the observed value of predictor X_j at location i , for $j = 1, \dots, p$. Let $\mathbf{D} = (d_{ik})_{i,k=1}^N$ denote the $N \times N$ distance matrix between census-tract representative locations, where d_{ik} is the distance between locations i and k . On the other hand, let $\mathbf{W}^{(i)} = \text{diag}(w_1^{(i)}, \dots, w_N^{(i)})$ be the spatial weight matrix associated with location i , with $w_i^{(i)} = 1$ and the remaining weights depending on the distances d_{ik} , $k \neq i$. The local regression coefficients are $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i^T = (\beta_{i0}, \beta_{i1}, \dots, \beta_{ip})$, for $i = 1, \dots, N$. For each location i , GWR estimates $\boldsymbol{\beta}_i$ as the solution of the local weighted least-squares problem

$$\min_{\boldsymbol{\beta}_i} f_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}_i),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} f_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}_i) &= \sum_{k=1}^N w_k^{(i)} \left(y_k - \beta_{i0} - \sum_{j=1}^p \beta_{ij} x_{kj} \right)^2 \\ &= \sum_{k=1}^N w_k^{(i)} \left(y_k - \mathbf{x}_k^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_i \right)^2. \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Consequently, the GWR calibration process can be interpreted as a collection of N independent local weighted regression problems. From classical regression theory, the solution of the previous problem is given by

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_i = \left(\mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{W}^{(i)} \mathbf{X} \right)^{-1} \mathbf{X}^T \mathbf{W}^{(i)} \mathbf{y}. \quad (3)$$

Regarding the specification of the spatial weights, in this work we have considered the bisquare function

$$w_k^{(i)} = \left(1 - \left(\frac{d_{ik}}{h} \right)^2 \right)^2, \quad \text{if } d_{ik} < h \text{ (and 0 otherwise),} \quad (4)$$

although other alternative weighting schemes have been proposed in the literature, see Brunson et al. (1996, 1998); Fotheringham et al. (2003). In (4), h denotes the bandwidth

parameter that controls the number of nearby locations contributing to the local estimation process. When h increases, more locations are incorporated into the local estimation process and the resulting regression estimates become closer to those obtained under the ordinary least squares approach. Conversely, as h approaches zero, fewer locations will be used to infer the coefficients resulting in larger estimation variances. Therefore, h needs to be carefully calibrated. In practice, the bandwidth parameter is commonly selected through a leave-one-out cross-validation procedure where the corresponding cross-validation score is given by

$$CV(h) = \sum_{i=1}^N [y_i - \hat{y}_{\neq i}(h)]^2,$$

where $\hat{y}_{\neq i}(h)$ denotes the fitted response value for location i when observation i is excluded from the local estimation process. Then, the optimal bandwidth parameter h^* is selected as

$$h^* = \arg \min_{h>0} CV(h).$$

Although GWR can provide highly accurate local predictions, the estimation process is exclusively driven by predictive performance and does not explicitly account for disparities between population groups. Consequently, the resulting predicted accessibility patterns may unintentionally reproduce or even amplify existing spatial inequalities present in the observed data. To evaluate this effect, we introduce a disparity measure associated with the predicted accessibility values. Analogously to the measure defined in (1) for the observed accessibility measurements, the predicted unfairness level associated with the regression model is defined as

$$u_{\hat{y}} = \left| \frac{1}{\text{card}(S)} \sum_{i \in S} \hat{y}_i - \frac{1}{\text{card}(\bar{S})} \sum_{i \in \bar{S}} \hat{y}_i \right|, \quad (5)$$

where $\hat{y}_i = \mathbf{x}_i^T \hat{\boldsymbol{\beta}}_i$ represents the predicted accessibility value for census tract i .

Consider the Seville UGS accessibility case study introduced in Section 2.3. The accessibility indicator Y is modeled through GWR using the seven socioeconomic attributes X_1, \dots, X_7

as explanatory variables. The resulting fitted model achieves a good predictive fit, as reflected by the strong spatial similarity between the observed and predicted accessibility patterns shown in Figure 5. Recall that, for the child-population attribute X_3 , the observed accessibility measurements exhibit a relative disparity of approximately 8.73%, corresponding to average accessibility values of 5577.40 and 5129.74 meters for the groups S and \bar{S} , respectively. After fitting the GWR model using the seven socioeconomic variables X_1, \dots, X_7 , the predicted accessibility values yield average group accessibility levels of 5586.38 and 5095.00 meters, respectively, leading to a predicted disparity value of approximately $u_{\hat{y}} = 491.37$ meters and a relative disparity of approximately 9.64%. This result illustrates that, since the GWR model accurately reproduces the underlying spatial structure of the observed accessibility data, the accessibility disparities already present in the original measurements are also preserved — and slightly amplified — in the resulting predictions.

Figure 5: Comparison between observed (left) and GWR-predicted (right) healthcare accessibility patterns in Seville.

3.2. A fair GWR formulation

As discussed in the previous section, GWR does not explicitly regulate accessibility disparities between sensitive population groups. Consequently, the resulting predictions may unintentionally preserve or even intensify such disparities. To address this issue, in this section we introduce a fairness-regularized extension of GWR aimed at explicitly controlling the

level of disparity present in the predicted accessibility values. More precisely, the proposed formulation incorporates the unfairness metric $u_{\hat{y}}$ defined in (5) directly into the regression calibration process through an explicit optimization constraint. The objective is therefore to reduce inequalities reflected in the predicted accessibility values while limiting, as much as possible, the associated loss in predictive accuracy. To this end, we propose the following fairness-regularized extension of GWR:

$$(P) \quad \begin{cases} \min_{\boldsymbol{\beta}_1, \dots, \boldsymbol{\beta}_N} & \sum_{i=1}^N f_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}_i) \\ \text{s.t.} & \left| \frac{1}{\text{card}(S)} \sum_{i \in S} \mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_i - \frac{1}{\text{card}(\bar{S})} \sum_{i \in \bar{S}} \mathbf{x}_i^T \boldsymbol{\beta}_i \right| \leq \varepsilon u_y, \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where $f_i(\boldsymbol{\beta}_i)$, defined in (2), denotes the local weighted least-squares objective associated with location i , and $\varepsilon \in (0, 1)$ is a user-defined fairness parameter controlling the maximum disparity allowed in the predicted accessibility values. Smaller values of ε impose stricter fairness requirements, progressively reducing the differences between the predicted average accessibility levels of groups S and \bar{S} . Alternatively, $(1 - \varepsilon) \times 100\%$ represents the target unfairness reduction level with respect to the disparity observed in the original accessibility measurements, u_y .

The formulation given by (6) leads to a constrained quadratic optimization problem whose computational resolution is discussed in Section 3.3. Note that the fairness constraint in (6) simultaneously involves all local parameter vectors through the predicted accessibility values. Consequently, unlike standard GWR, the model is no longer separable across spatial locations and must therefore be solved as a globally coupled optimization problem.

3.3. Optimization and implementation details

From a computational perspective, the resulting formulation as in (6) defines a convex quadratic optimization problem with linear inequality constraints. Indeed, the objective function is given by the sum of convex quadratic weighted least-squares terms, whereas the fairness restriction can be equivalently expressed through two linear inequality constraints

derived from the absolute-value disparity condition. The optimization problem is solved numerically as a constrained quadratic optimization problem.

The methodology has been implemented in R using the `quadprog` package. The optimization matrices are constructed from the design matrix, the observed accessibility values, and the spatial weighting matrices associated with the selected GWR kernel. When fairness constraints are omitted, the formulation naturally reduces to the classical GWR estimator.

Similarly to standard GWR methodologies, bandwidth selection in the fair GWR framework is performed through leave-one-out cross-validation. In practice, the cross-validation criterion is first evaluated over a grid of candidate bandwidth values and subsequently refined through bounded numerical optimization around the best candidate solution.

The complete methodology has been implemented in the open-source R package `fairgwr`, which provides routines for fairness-aware GWR calibration, bandwidth selection, disparity evaluation, and fairness-aware spatial prediction. In the interest of transparency and reproducibility, the package, together with usage documentation and reproducible examples, through the repository [Montero and Ramírez-Cobo \(2026\)](#).

4. Numerical results

This section illustrates the proposed fair GWR model using the two motivating examples described in Section 2.3. In the first experiment, addressed in Section 4.1, the fairness constraints are imposed globally across all census tracts in the study region. In contrast, the second experiment (Section 4.2) considers a territorially targeted setting in which the fairness constraints are applied only to a subset of particularly vulnerable census tracts. For both case studies, the fair GWR model is evaluated over a grid of unfairness-reduction levels ranging from 0% to 100% in increments of 10%. In order to avoid scale effects among predictors, all explanatory variables are standardized prior to model fitting. Finally, due to the illustrative nature of the experiments, no external validation or train–test partitioning strategy is considered in this work. Consequently, all reported predictions correspond to

in-sample fitted values obtained from the same datasets used during model calibration.

4.1. Fair GWR analysis for Urban Green Spaces accessibility in Seville

In this first numerical experiment, the proposed fair GWR methodology is applied to the Seville Urban Green Spaces (UGS) dataset introduced in Example 1 of Section 2.3. Recall that the observed accessibility measurements exhibit a relative disparity of approximately 8.7% between census tracts with higher and lower child-population levels. The objective of this experiment is therefore to reduce the disparities induced by the regression predictions while preserving, as much as possible, the predictive accuracy of the model. To this end, the fair GWR model introduced in Section 3 is fitted to the accessibility response variable and the seven socioeconomic predictors described in Section 2.3 under different target unfairness-reduction levels.

Figure 6 compares the observed accessibility values (Y , top panel) with the predicted values obtained under unfairness-reduction levels of 20%, 50%, and 80% (bottom panels). As the unfairness-reduction level increases, the predicted values progressively depart from the observed ones, reflecting the intrinsic trade-off between predictive accuracy and unfairness mitigation. This behaviour is quantitatively reflected in the evolution of the mean squared prediction error shown in the left panel of Figure 7, which generally increases under increasingly restrictive fairness constraints. Although the proposed optimization problem does not explicitly minimize the prediction error itself, stronger fairness requirements naturally tend to reduce predictive accuracy. For comparison, the right panel of Figure 7 presents the evolution of the objective function value. Unlike the prediction error, the objective function values are guaranteed to exhibit a monotone increasing behaviour, since the feasible regions associated with increasing unfairness-reduction levels form a nested sequence of progressively smaller constraint sets.

Table 2 reports the evolution of the predicted unfairness measure $u_{\hat{y}}$ under increasing unfairness-reduction levels. The results confirm that the proposed regularized formulation effectively controls the disparities induced by the regression model. In particular, the predicted

Figure 6: Top: observed average walking-distance values to Urban Green Spaces (UGS) across census tracts in Seville. Bottom: predicted values generated by the fair GWR model for unfairness-reduction levels of 20%, 50%, and 80% (from left to right). Increasing fairness constraints progressively modify the original distance patterns.

Figure 7: Evolution of the mean squared prediction error (left) and objective function value (right) as the unfairness-reduction level increases.

disparity decreases progressively as stricter fairness constraints are imposed, eventually reaching complete parity between the sensitive and non-sensitive groups under full unfairness reduction. It should be emphasized that the case corresponding to a 0% unfairness-reduction level does not coincide with the (unconstrained) GWR solution discussed in Section 3.1. Instead, it imposes the condition that the predicted unfairness level cannot exceed the disparity observed in the original accessibility data, that is, $u_{\hat{y}} \leq u_y$.

Table 2: Evolution of the predicted disparity under increasing unfairness-reduction levels.

Unfairness-reduction level	\bar{y}_S	$\bar{y}_{\bar{S}}$	$u_{\hat{y}}$	Relative disparity (%)
0%	5110.65	5558.31	447.66	8.76
10%	5125.94	5528.83	402.90	7.86
20%	5139.58	5497.71	358.13	6.97
30%	5152.13	5465.49	313.36	6.08
40%	5165.10	5433.70	268.60	5.20
50%	5178.29	5402.12	223.83	4.32
60%	5192.00	5371.07	179.07	3.45
70%	5205.61	5339.91	134.30	2.58
80%	5209.18	5298.72	89.53	1.72
90%	5223.31	5268.08	44.77	0.86
100%	5227.32	5227.32	0.00	0.00

The previous results illustrate how increasing unfairness-reduction levels progressively modify the predicted values \hat{y}_i , and affect both accuracy and optimization performance. It is also interesting to analyze how these fairness constraints alter the local regression coefficients. Figure 8 illustrates the estimated coefficients associated with predictors X_1 , X_3 , and X_8 (that, values of $\hat{\beta}_{i1}$, $\hat{\beta}_{i3}$ and $\hat{\beta}_{i8}$ for $i = 1, \dots, N$), under unfairness-reduction levels of 20%, 50%, and 80%. The results reveal substantial modifications in the spatial distribution of the estimated coefficients as the fairness constraints become more and more restrictive. In particular, several census tracts exhibit significant changes in the magnitude and even the sign of the estimated coefficients.

4.2. Targeted fair GWR analysis for healthcare accessibility in Seville

Unlike the previous experiment, where fairness constraints were imposed globally across the entire city, this second case study focuses on a territorially targeted fairness intervention.

Figure 8: Spatial distribution of the estimated regression coefficients associated with predictors X_1 , X_3 , and X_8 (rows) for unfairness-reduction levels of 20%, 50%, and 80% (columns).

More precisely, let G denote the set of census tracts belonging to the Este–Alcosa–Torreblanca district introduced in the second motivating example of Section 2.3. Figure 9 illustrates census tracts within this district, where dark-gray tracts correspond to lower-income areas and light-gray tracts correspond to higher-income areas. As discussed in Section 2, district G constitutes one of the areas in Seville exhibiting both comparatively lower socioeconomic conditions and poorer accessibility to healthcare facilities.

Figure 9: Income-based group classification within the Este–Alcosa–Torreblanca (G) district. Dark-gray census tracts correspond to the sensitive group S (lower-income areas), whereas light-gray census tracts belong to the complementary group \bar{S} (higher-income areas).

In this experiment, the sensitive group is defined as

$$S_g = S \cap G,$$

that is, the subset of low-income census tracts located within district G , depicted by dark-gray tracts by Figure 9. By restricting the fairness constraints to the territorially focused group S_g , the proposed fair GWR model emulates an urban-planning scenario in which accessibility improvements are explicitly prioritized for particularly vulnerable neighborhoods.

Figure 10 illustrates the observed and predicted distance values obtained under different unfairness-reduction levels. The left-column panels display the predicted values for the entire municipality of Seville, whereas the right-column panels focus exclusively on the targeted

district G . The first row corresponds to the observed distance values, while the remaining rows report the fair GWR predicted distances obtained under unfairness-reduction levels of 30%, 50%, and 90%, respectively. The results show that, as the fairness constraints become increasingly restrictive, the predicted accessibility conditions within the targeted vulnerable district progressively improve, as reflected by the lighter accessibility patterns observed in the right-column panels. At the same time, the municipality-wide maps indicate that these localized improvements are accompanied by noticeable modifications in other areas of the city. In particular, several central census tracts progressively exhibit darker red accessibility patterns as the unfairness-reduction level increases, reflecting higher predicted distance values and therefore a relative deterioration in accessibility conditions.

To further investigate the redistributive spatial effects suggested by Figure 10, Figure 11 provides a tract-level comparison between observed and predicted distances under a 50% unfairness-reduction level. The left panel corresponds to the sensitive census tracts belonging to the group $S_G = S \cap G$, whereas the right panel displays the remaining census tracts outside the sensitive group S_g . In the sensitive group (left panel), all observations are located below the diagonal reference line, indicating that the predicted distances are systematically lower than the observed values. Since lower distance values correspond to improved accessibility conditions, this behaviour reflects the intended effect of the imposed fairness constraint on the targeted vulnerable census tracts. In contrast, the right panel reveals that many census tracts outside the sensitive group exhibit predicted accessibility values above their observed levels, indicating a relative deterioration in predicted accessibility conditions for part of the remaining municipality.

From an exploratory perspective, these results may help identify which census tracts experience relative accessibility improvements or deteriorations under territorially targeted fairness constraints, potentially providing useful information for more informed urban-accessibility assessments.

Figure 10: Observed (first row) and predicted (rows 2-4) average walking-distance values to Healthcare Facilities in Seville under a territorially targeted fairness constraint. The left column shows the full municipality, whereas the right column focuses on the targeted vulnerable district *G*. Rows 2-4 show the fair GWR predictions under unfairness-reduction levels of 30%, 50%, and 90%, respectively.

Figure 11: Observed versus predicted distance values under a 50% unfairness-reduction level. Left: census tracts belonging to the sensitive group $S_g = S \cap G$. Right: remaining census tracts outside the sensitive group. The diagonal line represents perfect agreement between observed and predicted values.

5. Conclusions

This paper has introduced a fairness-constrained extension of the Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR) model for the analysis of spatial accessibility inequalities in urban environments. Motivated by the growing relevance of fairness-aware machine learning and by the urban-planning literature documenting accessibility disparities affecting vulnerable population groups, the proposed methodology incorporates fairness constraints into the GWR calibration process in order to regulate predictive disparities between sensitive and non-sensitive groups.

The proposed methodology has been illustrated through two case studies in the city of Seville involving accessibility to Urban Green Spaces and Healthcare Facilities. The numerical experiments demonstrated that the proposed methodology is capable of reducing predictive unfairness levels while revealing the corresponding trade-offs with predictive accuracy. In addition, the results have highlighted the existence of spatial redistributive effects induced by fairness constraints. From an exploratory perspective, the methodology may therefore provide useful information for identifying spatial patterns of accessibility gains and losses under different fairness scenarios.

To the best of our knowledge, this work constitutes one of the first attempts to explicitly incorporate fairness constraints into spatial predictive models in the context of urban planning.

In this sense, the proposed approach extends beyond the descriptive urban-inequality literature by incorporating fairness considerations directly into the predictive modeling stage. In the interest of transparency and reproducibility, all datasets, implementation details, and computational materials associated with this work have been made publicly available through the `fairgwr` R software package Montero and Ramírez-Cobo (2026).

Several limitations of the proposed methodology should be acknowledged. For example, the methodology is developed for a specific group-fairness measure. Alternative notions of fairness would generally require reformulating both the constrained optimization problem and the corresponding estimation procedure. On the other hand, the conclusions obtained from fairness-aware accessibility analyses should be interpreted with caution, since they strongly depend on the selected accessibility definition and the spatial scale of analysis. In particular, while the present study is conducted at census-tract level, fairness assessments are inherently conditional on the chosen spatial aggregation. Due to the Modifiable Areal Unit Problem (MAUP), the resulting conclusions may not remain invariant under alternative zoning schemes or aggregation structures. Consequently, the proposed methodology should not be interpreted as a fully prescriptive decision-making tool, but rather as a complementary exploratory framework capable of assisting urban analysts and planners in evaluating the potential spatial implications of fairness-aware predictive models.

Several future research directions naturally emerge from this work. Possible extensions include the incorporation of alternative fairness criteria, individual- or group-fairness notions, multiscale or robust GWR formulations, spatio-temporal fairness-aware regression models and other spatial machine-learning methodologies beyond GWR.

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